

Bridging R&D and production in semiconductor manufacturing

Best practice category

Strengthening manufacturing capacities, Materials, chemicals and equipment, Partner collaboration and open ecosystems

Stakeholder group

SMEs and start-ups, Research and Academia

Value chain position

Equipment, R&D, Fabrication

General Information

Chipmetrics is a leading Finnish company in **3D metrology** for semiconductors, co-founded with the support of the European Union and specialised in the development of innovative metrology chips and wafers for the control of production processes. Its **cutting-edge** solutions find application in thin film development, instrument qualification and quality assurance in the production of semiconductors and advanced materials.

Chipmetrics is recognised as a leading expert in measuring thin film compliance through the use of high aspect ratio **3D** test elements, a technology that enables extremely precise analysis and is a benchmark for industry.

The company focuses its business on overcoming the gap between research and production, ensuring that innovations developed in **R&D** can be scaled efficiently to **mass production**.

Activities and best practices

- A strategic area of activity of Chipmetrics concerns the improvement of efficiency in the processes of tool qualification and control of production processes in the manufacture of semiconductors. In this context, the company developed the PillarHall® approach, a technology that allows the conformality of thin films deposited via **Atomic Layer Deposition (ALD)** to be verified with an unprecedented level of precision and speed. Traditionally, instrument qualification takes several hours, often up to a full day, to complete the necessary analyses after maintenance or machine downtime. With the use of **PillarHall®** chips, this time is reduced to less than an hour, allowing a rapid return to production and more stable control of manufacturing lines.

- A central pillar of Chipmetrics activity is supporting the scalability of semiconductor processes, that is, the transition from research and development (**R & D**) phases to **large-scale production**. This phase represents one of the most delicate moments in the life cycle of a new technology. To bridge this gap, Chipmetrics has developed the 300mm Pocket Wafer, an innovative tool designed to facilitate the scalability of processes from the laboratory phase to industrial production. The wafer integrates **PillarHall®** chips in a standard 300mm format, enabling direct comparison and subsequent optimisation of processes at different scales. This represents a key element in ensuring continuity between academic innovation and industrial production, ensuring that laboratory-born discoveries can be implemented quickly in high-volume production environments.
- Amid an increasingly global semiconductor value chain, Chipmetrics is strengthening its international presence, with a focus on strategic markets in **East Asia**, especially in **Japan**, a key area for the development of advanced semiconductors. In 2025, the company opened an office in **Tokyo**. Japan represents one of the most advanced markets in the world for the production of new generation **logic** and **memories**, areas in which Chipmetrics metrology solutions play a crucial role in guaranteeing precision, quality and repeatability of processes. The local presence makes it possible to respond more quickly and in a targeted manner to the needs of manufacturers and research centres, encouraging continuous technical dialogue and the adaptation of solutions to specific market requirements.
- Chipmetrics is also a member of the JETRO IBSC (Japan External Trade Organization Incubation Program) in **Tokyo**, which supports foreign technology companies in entering and developing their businesses in Japan. At the same time, Chipmetrics is also expanding its business in **South Korea**, another strategic market for the production of semiconductors, in particular **DRAM** and **NAND**, where **Atomic Layer Deposition (ALD)** technologies are essential for improving device performance. The expansion into **Asia** is a key step in Chipmetrics international growth strategy, aimed at strengthening technical support to customers and fostering new industrial and scientific collaborations.

Challenges addressed with this practice

Chipmetrics addresses one of the main challenges of the semiconductor industry: effectively and quickly transfer laboratory-developed innovations to large-scale manufacturing, while ensuring precision, repeatability and process control. At the same time, its growing international presence, particularly in Japan and East Asia, responds to the need for greater integration into the global value chain and constant technical dialogue between research, suppliers and manufacturers. This approach makes it possible to bridge the gap between R & D and production, supporting the competitiveness of the sector and promoting more efficient, precise and sustainable semiconductor manufacturing.